

ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL-BASED CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING THE NOBLE MORALS OF MA STUDENTS (CASE STUDY ON MA HIDAYATUL INSAN PALANGKA RAYA CITY AND MA TAHFIDZ NURUL MUSTHOFA TANJUNG)

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Abstract

The Islamic boarding school-based curriculum implemented at MA is a form of internalizing the values desired by Islamic boarding schools into the National Curriculum. This research generally aims to describe and analyze Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving students' noble morals, the specific aim is to describe and analyze planning, organizing, implementation, evaluation, problems and solutions for Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving MA students' noble morals. The theories used are Terry's management theory, Tylor's curriculum theory, and Al Ghazali's Noble Akhlak theory. The approach used is a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection techniques are: interviews, observation and documentation studies. Research results: 1) Islamic boarding school-based curriculum planning has been formulated and determined through deliberation stages involving caregivers, madrasa heads, teacher councils, and educational staff; 2) Curriculum organization is carried out with a division of work and workload that is adjusted to the content of the MA curriculum, but is still constrained by educational resources, not all of whom are competent in their fields; 3) The implementation of the curriculum is based on the national curriculum structure which is integrated with the unique values of Islamic boarding schools with references to classical books, but several problems are still found, including the ability of educators to explain the material and combine noble moral values which still need to be improved as well as limited learning resources. ; 4) Curriculum evaluation has not been used optimally as material for consideration and study in making curriculum improvements; 5) Curriculum management problems are still faced with the constraints of educational backgrounds of teaching staff which are still not appropriate, funding which is still not sufficient for operational needs, as well as limited infrastructure and learning resources; 6) Curriculum management solutions are carried out by increasing the capabilities of teaching staff in Islamic boarding school specific subjects, collaborating with various parties to explore funding sources, and fulfilling standardized infrastructure in accordance with established regulations. In general, the results of this research conclude that Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management has been implemented based on the national curriculum which is integrated with the values desired by the Islamic boarding school, but has not fully had an impact on improving the noble morals of MA students.

Keywords: Management of Curriculum, Noble Morals.

INTRODUCTION

Islamic boarding schools are traditional Islamic educational institutions that aim to understand, appreciate and practice Islamic teachings by emphasizing the importance of religious morals as a guide to social life. As a religious educational institution, Islamic boarding schools have their own characteristics and characteristics and are different when compared to other educational institutions (Susilo & Kartowagiran, 2023). Islamic boarding

schools as Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia, which in the early stages before the introduction of Islamic reform ideas into Indonesia, solely taught classical books with the aim of forming ulama, Kiai who were competent in the field of Islamic sciences. After the flow of progress over time was accompanied by the entry of reforming ideas from Islamic thinkers into Indonesia, Islamic boarding schools have experienced dynamics. These dynamics can be seen from three aspects, material dynamics (the material being taught), administration and management dynamics (Nuryakhman, 2021).

Islamic boarding schools are traditional Islamic educational institutions that aim to understand, appreciate and practice Islamic teachings by emphasizing the importance of religious morals as a guide to life in society (Salingkat et al., 2023). As a religious educational institution, Islamic boarding schools have their own characteristics and characteristics and are different when compared to other educational institutions (Sholah & Mawaddah, 2023).

In general, Islamic boarding schools can be divided into two, namely Salafiyah Islamic boarding schools and Khalafiyah Islamic boarding schools (Fadillah et al., 2021). Salafiyah Islamic boarding schools are Islamic boarding schools in which there is a Salaf education system (wetonan and sorogan) and a Salaf classical system (madrasah). Meanwhile, Kholafiyah Islamic boarding schools, namely Islamic boarding schools in which there is a more complete Salaf and classical education system, because apart from public schools there are also the addition of Diniyah, universities, cooperatives, and Arabic-English special education (Sriartha et al., 2021).

Islamic boarding schools are educational institutions that developed earlier than formal educational institutions that were introduced during colonialism. Islamic boarding schools grow and develop according to the sociocultural dynamics that surround society (Ulum & Riswadi, 2023). Until now, Islamic boarding schools still exist amidst the rapid development of science and technology with adaptation according to the demands of the times (Husnani et al., 2020). For this reason, the Islamic boarding school education system is recognized as an indigenous (original) Indonesian educational institution which is different from educational patterns in other countries (Rulitawati et al., 2020).

UU no. 18 of 2019 concerning Islamic boarding schools has become a new milestone in the history of Islamic education traditions in Indonesia, especially for community-based education models. The definition of Islamic boarding school education includes models of educational institutions such as Islamic boarding schools, dayah, surau, meunasah (madrasah), and others, whether managed by non-government or private companies or managed by the government. Indonesian society is increasingly aware of the importance of Islamic boarding schools as a model of Islamic education, even though it was born from past traditions (Minarti et al., 2022).

Islamic boarding schools have very noble ideals and goals, which in the Islamic Boarding School Law states that the purpose of Islamic boarding school educational institutions is to;

- a) Form individuals who excel in various fields who understand and practice the values of their religious teachings and/or become experts in religious knowledge who are faithful, devout, have noble character, knowledge, independence, mutual assistance, balance and moderation;
- b) Forming a moderate understanding of religion and diversity and love of the country and forming behavior that encourages the creation of religious harmony; and
- c) Improving the quality of life of empowered communities in meeting the educational needs of citizens and the social welfare of the community.

As an educational institution, Islamic boarding schools, in their development, strive to adapt their curriculum models to the circumstances and progress of the situation (Hashim et al., 2023). Islamic boarding school is an educational unit which contains the study of the Yellow Book or Islamic teachings, both in a tiered and non-graded manner (Astuti et al., 2020). The great demand from society is that they want education that not only teaches general sciences but also emphasizes attitudes and behavior for students (Kultsum et al., 2022). This reality requires Islamic boarding schools to be able to create a curriculum that is relevant to developments in science and the demands of the times so that Islamic boarding schools are able to innovate and are not abandoned by society (Thohari & Chotimah, 2021).

To achieve the desired goals, Islamic boarding schools must have a foresight in order to be able to bring their students to compete in the modern and digital era (Suparjo et al., 2021). Therefore, good curriculum management is needed in order to achieve the desired goals so that it can support the continuity of education in Islamic boarding schools. This is because the curriculum is one of the pieces of software that is urgently needed to be updated according to current developments (Muthoharoh & Miftahuddin, 2021). The success of the curriculum can be influenced by empowerment in the field of management or administration in the educational institution concerned and is often termed curriculum management (Muslim et al., 2020). Curriculum management is one aspect that influences the success of learning in national education (Bahroni et al., 2020). In addition, the curriculum is a system of learning programs to achieve institutional goals in educational institutions, so that the curriculum plays an important role in creating quality schools (Nurasiah et al., 2022). To support the success of the curriculum, efforts are needed to empower the field of management or curriculum management (Muassomah et al., 2022)

Islamic boarding school curriculum management steps can be carried out through planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating Good curriculum management will of course be able to improve the quality of the Islamic boarding school itself, especially in improving students' noble morals, in accordance with the aim of Islamic boarding schools, not only to teach students to understand their religious teachings, but also to make religion a cornerstone of their daily lives (Siregar et al., 2023). The curriculum in the world of Islamic boarding schools is preserved through the teaching of classical and cultural books which have become the

characteristics of Islamic boarding schools (Idrus & Muhammad, 2023). Remembering that the aim of Islamic boarding schools is not only to teach students to understand the teachings of their religion, but also to make religion and morals the basis for their daily life (Subaidi et al., 2023). Morals are the will of the soul contained within every human being which gives rise to actions easily, be they good or bad, without requiring prior consideration of the mind (Windiasih et al., 2022). Moral development is very necessary in modern times because moral development of students is something that everyone desires in the educational process, because morals have the function of making human behavior more civilized and being able to identify various life problems, good or bad according to applicable norms (Anggraeni et al., 2023) We cannot deny the reality that we are currently facing. The development of information technology, especially social media, has a very negative influence on the attitudes and behavior of teenagers. We often hear news both through print and electronic media and even social media about behavior. deviant behavior that indicates the moral decline of teenagers (Anwar et al., 2023). The issue of student morals is now a serious concern not only in the context of the curriculum but more broadly in the field of education (Hanafiah et al., 2022). The formation of morals can be done through education, training, hard work and coaching, it does not happen by itself, or in other words it is difficult for someone to apply a moral act without knowing, understanding, studying and practicing, as well as providing guidance on the formation of the morals themselves, through an educational process (Fitri et al., 2021). One of the Madrasah Aliyah which organizes an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum to improve students' noble morals is MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung. MA as a senior secondary education unit within the Ministry of Religion needs to implement an MA curriculum that refers to National Education Standards. The preparation of the MA Curriculum is intended to ensure the achievement of national education goals. National education standards consist of: content standards, process standards, graduate competency standards, standards for educators and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure standards, management standards, financing standards and education assessment standards. Through this Islamic boarding school-based curriculum, it is hoped that the implementation of educational programs at MA will be in accordance with the potential characteristics and needs of students. For this reason, its preparation needs to involve all Madrasah residents and other stakeholders. Based on a preliminary study regarding Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving students' noble morals at MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung, several problems were encountered including;

- 1) The learning load received increases;
- 2) There is a reduction in the number of hours of certain lessons to be filled in boarding school subjects;
- 3) The assessment system has become complicated;
- 4) Focusing on which curriculum is prioritized;
- 5) There is a mismatch in educational qualifications that are not in accordance with the subject matter being taught.

This certainly has an impact on the fulfillment of student competencies. Apart from that, the number of teaching staff needed is also increasing and this has an impact on increasing funding

As the MA which implements the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum, MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung as the locus of research are based on several reasons including:

- 1) MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung are MAs located in the province different, namely Central Kalimantan and South Kalimantan;
- 2) MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung have relatively the same curriculum characteristics
- 3) MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung implement a curriculum with the same subject content.

The problem of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving students' noble morals at MA is a problem that continues to develop in the aspects of planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. This problem is triggered by the lack of optimal student empowerment, the commitment of madrasa heads and teachers and madrasa committees. Other things that exacerbate the problem of improving students' noble morals are the involvement of parents, teaching human resources and educational staff who are less competent, the availability of facilities and financing is still limited, so this has quite an impact on efforts to improve students' noble morals. This condition makes it increasingly difficult for madrasas to achieve the goals of MA students who are *uswatun hasanah*.

Apart from that, the root of the problem is the problem of curriculum management itself which has not been organized well enough, so that it not only has an impact on students' noble morals but can also have an impact on the quality of learning and ultimately have an impact on student achievement and the quality of MA graduates. Based on these problems, this research aims to determine management planning, organizing, implementing, evaluating, problems and solutions for Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA students at MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung.

RESEARCH METHODS

Based on a descriptive approach with case studies at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfiz Nurul Mosthofa Tanjung and the types of data used in research on Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving students' noble morals at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung. The data analyzed in it is descriptive and not in the form of numbers as is the case in quantitative research. The data that will be revealed in this research are: planning, organizing, implementing, evaluating, problems and solutions, approaches and types of data used in

Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management research in improving students' noble morals at MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung.

Data Collection Technique

Qualitative data collection techniques are approaches used to collect information that is non-numerical (does not contain numbers) and is usually found in qualitative research. Qualitative data can reveal concepts, opinions, or experiences that are not easy to quantify or measure. Data collection techniques are the most important step in research, because the main aim of research is to obtain data. According to (Sugiyono, 2011) in qualitative research, data collection can be carried out in natural settings, primary or secondary data sources, and in various ways. And data collection can be done by observation, interviews, documentation, questionnaires. Data collection techniques are used to obtain the data needed in research, the techniques that will be used in this research are as follows:

Interview

Interviews are the form of data collection most often used in qualitative research. Nurses often think interviews are easy because in their daily lives, nurses often communicate with their clients to get important information. This in-depth interview method is used to interview the Head of the Madrasah Education Section, the Head of the Diniyah and Islamic Boarding School Education Section, the Madrasah Head, the Deputy Head of the Madrasah for Curriculum and the Board of Teachers. It is used to reveal data or information regarding planning, organizing, implementation, evaluation, problems, solutions. From the problems of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA students at MAN Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung. The in-depth interview technique used in this research is part of the qualitative method. In this qualitative method, it is known as an in-depth interview technique. The definition of an in-depth interview is the process of obtaining information for research purposes by means of face-to-face questions and answers between the interviewer and the respondent or person being interviewed, with or without using an interview guide where the interviewer and informant are involved in social life. Relatively long.

Observation

Participant observation is a person's ability to use their observations through the work of the five senses of the eyes, ears, and with the help of other five senses. Observation is essentially an activity using the five senses, including sight, smell, hearing, to obtain the information needed to answer research problems. The results of observations are activities, incidents, events, objects, certain conditions or atmosphere, and a person's emotional feelings. Observations are carried out to obtain a real picture of an event or events to answer research questions. Observations made by researchers include improving Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving students' noble morals at MAN Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung in the form of learning activities, activities to strengthen students' noble morals both in the madrasah environment and in the dormitory environment.

Documentation

The documentation method is a data collection method, by searching for data or information, which has been recorded/published in several existing documents, such as master books, personal books, and other certificates. According to (Sugiyono, 2017) states that documents are records of past events. Documents can be in the form of images, writing or monumental works of someone. According to (Kadir & Rama, 2023) state that documents can be in the form of printed or written recordings of past events, can be in the form of anecdotal notes, diaries, letters and documents. This method is used by researchers to record the history of the establishment and description of the research locus, and documents related to planning, organizing, implementing, evaluating, problems, solutions to Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management problems in improving the noble morals of MA students at MAN Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung.

Data Collection Instrument

No	Research purposes	Research Indicators	Data source	Research Techniques		
				W	O	SD
1	Planning	a. Needs analysis b. philosophical; curriculum c. Curriculum design d. Master plan, development, implementation and assessment.	1) Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Palangka Raya City and Tabalong Regency 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Ministry of Religion of Palangka Raya City and Tabalong Regency 4) Head of MA Hidayatul Insan City of Palangka Raya and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung 5) Deputy Head of Curriculum Affairs MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung 6) Council of Teachers MA Hidayatul Insan City of Palangka Raya and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung	√	-	√
2	Organizing	a. Rational formulation or basic thinking b. Vision, mission and goals c. Program structure and content; d. selection and organization of material;	1) Head of Madrasah Education 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Head of the Supreme Court 4) Deputy Head of Curriculum 5) Teachers' council	√	-	√

		e. organizing learning activities; f. Resources, tools and learning facilities				
3	Implementation	a. Learning plans and programs (syllabus, lesson plans) b. Explanation of material c. Learning strategies and methods d. Resources, tools and learning facilities e. Methods and tools for assessing learning processes and outcomes f. Environment settings	1) Head of Madrasah Education 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Head of the Supreme Court 4) Deputy Head of Curriculum 5) Teachers' council	√	√	√
4	Evaluation	1) Evaluation Aspect 2) Evaluation Techniques 3) Analysis of Evaluation Results	1) Head of Madrasah Education 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Head of the Supreme Court 4) Deputy Head of Curriculum 5) Teachers' council	√	√	√
5	Problem	a. Human Resources for Educators and Education Personnel b. Financing c. Infrastructure	1) Head of Madrasah Education 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Head of the Supreme Court 4) Deputy Head of Curriculum 5) Teachers' council	√	√	√
6	Solution	a. Human Resources for Educators and Education Personnel b. Financing c. Infrastructure	1) Head of Madrasah Education 2) Head of Early Education and Islamic Boarding School 3) Head of the Supreme Court 4) Deputy Head of Curriculum 5) Teachers' council			

Note: (W) Interview, (O) Observation, (SD) Documentation Study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya

1) Islamic boarding school-based curriculum planning in improving the noble morals of MA Hidayatul Insan students in Palangka City

Planning is a process of determining the goals to be achieved, what actions need to be taken to achieve these goals and how to arrange the steps effectively and determine the stages needed to achieve them. The results of research in the field are based on documentation studies, observations and interviews related to needs analysis that in improving curriculum management, namely by observing and reviewing the curriculum which contains basic material that can be applied and needed by students according to the characteristics of students and the madrasah environment and in accordance with the demands of society, with the quality of graduates who are expected to be of benefit to society, especially in terms of responding to and helping guide society in religious matters. What institutions do to improve curriculum management based on environmental needs is to carry out initial observations and review the curriculum which contains basic material that suits the needs of students and the institutional environment. MA looks at the surrounding environment and then prepares a curriculum based on the needs and interests of the surrounding environment so that graduates can help meet the needs of the environment in terms of social, current developments and of course also religion. Assessed with students' human resources needs. Community involvement in curriculum management so that they can understand, assist and control curriculum implementation, so that educational institutions are not only required to be cooperative but also able to be independent

2) Organizing an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum to improve the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City

Organizing is the process of dividing work into small tasks, assigning these tasks to people according to their abilities, and allocating resources and coordinating them in order to effectively achieve organizational goals. Organization is very necessary in management because with an organizing system, it will be easy for management to carry out control and supervision and find out where management deficiencies are so that they can be corrected, and management goals can be achieved easily. Based on the results of field notes from interviews and document studies, the rational formulation or rationale for Islamic boarding school-based curriculum is to look at the challenges of globalization and the environment around the institution, which places demands on every individual in society, apart from having general knowledge, every student must also be able to have knowledge. religion in balance with general knowledge The rational formulation or basic thinking about the Islamic boarding school curriculum is to look at the challenges of globalization and the environment around the Islamic boarding school, which places demands on every individual in society, apart from having general knowledge, every student must also be able to have religious abilities that are balanced with general knowledge to answer religious problems that exist in society when they return to society. The Islamic boarding school-based curriculum is a form of meeting community needs

in the field of religion. The formulation is based on the needs of society or the environment to support the competitiveness of students from other public schools so that they are able to compete not only in general knowledge but also in the field of religion in order to be able to guide society from a spiritual perspective. Curriculum from the Ministry of Religion with integration of the modern Islamic boarding school curriculum. The Islamic boarding school curriculum is a tool for achieving educational goals, as well as a guideline for implementing education that reflects the nation's outlook on life.

3) Implementation of an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City

Implementation is an action aimed at ensuring that all group members strive to achieve targets in accordance with managerial planning and organizational efforts. Basically, actuating is an effort to move all group members to be willing to work together to achieve the desired goals. This activity has a very important role in the management process of an educational organization. Based on field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, the preparation of the syllabus and lesson plans is based on a combination of the K13 curriculum and the independent curriculum based on the ministry of religion, as well as the boarding school curriculum which is adopted/based on the Gontor modern boarding school curriculum. The preparation of the syllabus and RPP is based on a combination of the curriculum used, namely curriculum 13 and the independent curriculum based on the ministry of religion, as well as the boarding school curriculum which is adopted/based on the Gontor modern boarding school curriculum. Curriculum 13 and the independent curriculum are combined according to the Ministry of Religion. The boarding school lessons follow the Gontor boarding school curriculum. Create learning objectives and flow of learning objectives. Reviewing Competency Standards and Basic Competencies, Identifying Main/Learning Materials, Developing Learning Activities, Formulating Indicators for Competency Achievement, Determining Types of Assessment, Determining Time Allocation, Determining Learning Resources.

4) Evaluation of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of MA Hidayatul Insan students in Palangka Raya City

Evaluation is part of the management system, namely planning, organization, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. The curriculum is also designed from the planning, organization, then implementation and finally monitoring and evaluation stages. Without evaluation, you will not know what the condition of the curriculum is in terms of design, implementation and results. Based on field notes from interviews, observations and documentation studies, aspects of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum evaluation were determined based on the results of a joint study with the MA Hidayatul Insan curriculum development team, chaired by the deputy head of the madrasah for curriculum. The aspect of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum evaluation that is evaluated is the achievement of the objectives of curriculum formulation, implementation/implementation of the curriculum and the products/results obtained from implementing the curriculum which are based on the objectives of implementing the curriculum. Aspects of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum evaluation are determined based on the results of a joint study with the MA Hidayatul Insan curriculum

development team, chaired by the deputy head of the madrasah for curriculum. The aspect of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum evaluation that is evaluated is the achievement of the objectives of curriculum formulation, implementation/implementation of the curriculum and the products/results obtained from implementing the curriculum which are based on the objectives of implementing the curriculum. Determined through the results of a joint evaluation with the teacher council regarding the students' ability to understand and practice the material being taught and its relevance to the students' needs when they enter society. Evaluation activities are carried out when there is an evaluation meeting. The evaluation of the curriculum is correct, firstly, by implementing the Islamic boarding school curriculum, it is able to address the various characteristics of students, secondly, by having the Islamic boarding school curriculum, it is able to provide optimal education at a higher level, thirdly, parents are more enthusiastic. The curriculum evaluation technique used is educational system evaluation, namely an evaluation technique carried out on all planned curriculum programs, the results achieved, input and the implementation process carried out. The curriculum evaluation technique used is educational system evaluation. Namely, evaluation techniques are carried out on all planned curriculum programs, the results achieved, input and the implementation process carried out. Planning, evaluation and deliberation. The technique of meeting first is carried out. Written test and oral exam.

5) Problems of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA Hidayatul Insan students, Palangka Raya City

Based on the results of field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, the problem with the human resource aspect of students' noble morals is the lack of available learning time. The problem with the human resource aspect of students' noble morals is the lack of available learning time. The learning duration is too short so that learning is not optimal. Plus, each child has their own innate character before entering MA which of course requires a process for new habits, including ethical methods. Teachers need to be improved in academic and non-academic quality. Lack of student discipline. The problem is related to the infrastructure that is owned, namely classrooms, LCD projectors and laptops to support the improvement of students' noble morals. Problems related to the infrastructure that is owned are classrooms, LCD projectors and laptops to support the improvement of students' noble morals. Classes require air conditioning such as fans. The hot conditions in the room make it difficult for students to focus on studying. There are holes in the blackboard, sometimes teachers have difficulty conveying material through writing. There are not enough cleaning tools, which makes the room look dirty, which of course affects comfort when studying. Speakers and projectors in the classroom. Lack of trash cans and no lab available. The problem related to financing is the lack of budget allocated for improving quality and curriculum management. Problems related to financing include a lack of budget allocated for improving the quality and management of the curriculum, especially the budget for efforts to increase teacher competency, the availability of learning facilities, as well as several infrastructure facilities that are less standardized. Lack of budget for facilities, means and infrastructure to support learning. The reduction in BOS funds created a funding shortage. Funding still relies on donations from donors, and also comes from the Islamic Boarding School Foundation.

6) Solutions implemented to overcome the problem of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA Hidayatul Insan students, Palangka Raya City

The solution to the problem of human resource aspects in improving students' noble morals is to modify the duration of learning time related to morals and synchronization as well as additional activities outside of learning hours related to improving students' noble morals. The solution to the problem of human resource aspects in improving students' noble morals is to modify the duration of learning time related to morals and synchronization as well as additional activities outside of learning hours related to improving students' noble morals. Increase learning duration, Guidance for teachers in improving teaching methods. Motivation so that teachers remain enthusiastic in teaching, make an emotional approach and relationship first with students so that it is easy to convey advice to them and we know the background and problems that cause them to be slow in developing a good personality. Conduct comparative studies with superior schools to imitate and develop their methods in improving students' noble morals. Teachers can make improvements with each subject of character education cultivation. The solution to the problem of the MA financing aspect in curriculum management is to budget funds for the next period and make a breakthrough by maximizing existing funds so that the development of students' noble morals can run well. The solution to the problem of the MA financing aspect in curriculum management is to budget funds for the next period and make a breakthrough by maximizing existing funds so that the development of students' noble morals continues to run well. Save money on things that are less urgent, for example the budget for certain events is temporarily simplified to save money, so that the remaining funds can be allocated for developing curriculum management and learning purposes. Quantity can be added to the financing. There is no solution that must be provided because there is no problem in the financing aspect. The solution to the MA infrastructure problem is carried out by allocating a budget in the following year to procure the infrastructure that is lacking and for current activities, moral development in the use of infrastructure can be maximized by combining classes, namely in classes that have fairly complete infrastructure. The solution to the MA infrastructure problem is carried out by allocating a budget in the following year to procure the infrastructure that is lacking and for current activities, moral development in the use of infrastructure is carried out by combining classes, namely in classes that have fairly complete infrastructure. Registration fees and tuition fees have been increased, God willing, parents/guardians of students will not protest if the increase is accompanied by improving the quality of school facilities and infrastructure. Improving the function of school cooperatives by opening a business and adding links/subscriptions and publishing them so that they are known to many people so that they can advance the business and school budget income. Take preventive action by making certain rules or sanctions for students who damage school facilities. So that there are tools for the teaching and learning process. Gradually complete and maintain existing infrastructure.

MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa

1) Islamic boarding school-based curriculum planning in improving the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

The curriculum itself is a plan to get the expected output (out comes) from learning. This plan is structured in a structured manner for a field of study, so as to provide guidelines and instructions for developing learning strategies (Material in the curriculum must be well organized so that the educational goals and objectives that have been set can be achieved. Based on the results of interview field notes documentation studies, needs analysis is carried out by distributing questionnaires and/or questionnaires to students and also Madrasah Aliyah teachers. By carrying out approach analysis, by distributing questionnaires and/or questionnaires to students and also teachers. namely by knowing the number of students, number of teachers and teaching staff, facilities and infrastructure, vision, mission and goals to improve curriculum management. Community involvement in curriculum management so that they can understand, assist and control curriculum implementation, so that educational institutions are not only required to be cooperative but are also able to be independent in identifying curriculum needs. There should be training related to the curriculum. The curriculum is a series of lessons prepared to achieve educational goals in making the life of the nation, state and religion more intelligent. So far, the curriculum has been formulated based on needs analysis according to environmental conditions in the madrasa. Philosophical curriculum is a series of learning that is designed in such a way as to achieve certain goals in learning. Know the vision and mission of the Islamic boarding school. The curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding objectives, content, and learning materials as well as materials used as guidelines for implementing learning activities to achieve certain educational goals. By studying first.

2) Organizing an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum to improve the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

Based on the results of field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, the organization of an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum is a curriculum that is developed in the form of experiences given to students while participating in daily activities within the educational framework. Based on the environmental conditions around the school, many parents are interested in sending their children to Islamic boarding schools to support good religious knowledge. However, in order to be able to continue to a higher level (college) a high school/MA level diploma is required. This is what underlies the formation of an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum, so that Islamic boarding school-based schools can study general lessons to support student learning. by creating a generation that excels in science and technology and IMPAQ. The Islamic boarding school curriculum is a tool for achieving educational goals, as well as a guideline for implementing education that reflects the nation's outlook on life. Increasing the Qur'an generation.

3) Implementation of an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

Based on the results of field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, the implementation of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum is carried out by the respective subject teachers. The preparation of lesson plans and so on is carried out by each teacher according to the subjects being taught. Steps for Preparing a RPP Include Identity. Formulate Learning Objectives. Determining Learning Materials. Determining Learning Methods. Determining Learning Activities. Selecting Learning Resources. Determining Valuation. Reviewing Competency Standards and Basic Competencies. Identifying Main/Learning Material. Developing Learning Activities. Formulating Competency Achievement Indicators. Determining the Type of Assessment. Determining Time Allocation. Determining Learning Resources. Work according to the learning material. One of the materials for improving students' noble morals that is arranged in the curriculum and applied to each subject is the habit of praying together before starting learning activities and reminding students to tidy up the classroom environment at the end of each lesson. One of the materials for improving students' noble morals that is arranged in the curriculum and applied to each subject is the habit of praying together before starting learning activities and reminding students to tidy up the classroom environment at the end of each lesson. Learning material related to etiquette towards Allah, towards fellow humans, qualities that Muslims should avoid and possess. In implementing character education for moral formation, learning planning needs to be developed to coordinate the moral characteristics that will be formed with other learning components, namely core standards, competency standards and basic competencies, standard materials, learning outcome indicators, and assessments.

4) Evaluation of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

Curriculum evaluation is the process of applying scientific procedures to collect valid and reliable data to make decisions about the curriculum that is currently running or has been implemented. This curriculum evaluation can cover the entire curriculum or each curriculum component such as objectives, content, or learning methods in the curriculum. Based on the results of field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, it was determined based on memorization, practice, experience and moral quality. Aspects of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum are based on memorizing deposits as well as several assessments on boarding school subjects. The curriculum evaluation carried out includes objectives, content, learning strategies, media, and so on. The evaluation of the curriculum is correct, firstly, by implementing the Islamic boarding school curriculum, it is able to address the various characteristics of students, secondly, by having the Islamic boarding school curriculum, it is able to provide optimal education at a higher level, thirdly, parents are more enthusiastic. Input evaluation techniques, curriculum implementation, and product evaluation Input evaluation techniques, curriculum implementation, and product evaluation. There are stages in carrying out an evaluation, namely: designing, preparing, collecting information, analyzing, making conclusions, making recommendations, and utilizing the evaluation results. Forms of

curriculum evaluation analysis include looking at student learning outcomes. Forms of curriculum evaluation analysis include looking at student learning outcomes. One form of curriculum evaluation is formative evaluation, which is an evaluation carried out to improve and improve the learning and teaching process. Formative evaluation, is an assessment carried out with the aim of monitoring and improving the learning process, as well as evaluating the achievement of learning objectives) and summative (assessment which aims to assess students' achievement of learning objectives and/or Learning Achievements (CP), as a basis for determining grade promotion and/ or graduation from an educational unit). Written and oral exams. Strive to develop effective learning methods and models. Strive to develop effective learning methods and models. Improving the substance of the curriculum, curriculum implementation procedures, instructional methods, and their impact on student learning and behavior. Evaluation of the teaching and learning process, evaluation of learning materials, evaluation of the success (product) of the curriculum.

5) Problems of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

Based on the results of field notes from interviews, observations and document studies, incompetent teaching and education staff. Educators are still unable to develop their abilities due to a lack of supporting tools during the learning process. Student discipline and cleanliness Lack of student discipline. There isn't any. Periodic maintenance of infrastructure facilities, due to inadequate maintenance costs for infrastructure facilities. Funding sources only depend on BOS so they cannot be optimal in supporting the quality of the curriculum. Construction still underway. Lack of trash bins and no lab available. IPA. Facilities are not enough. Financing problems are still constrained, existing funds are mostly used for operational needs, such as teacher salaries, routine costs and other funds. There are still many infrastructure facilities that do not yet exist, such as laboratories.

6) Solutions implemented to overcome the problem of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung students

Based on the results of field notes, interviews, observations and document studies. Participate in training or seminars. By providing tools and infrastructure to support teacher performance. How to Improve the Quality of Human Resources Carrying out education and coaching. The aim is to develop individuals, in terms of increasing the individual's knowledge, skills and attitudes. There needs to be special guidance for students. There isn't any. It is hoped that we can work together to carry out regular maintenance of facilities and infrastructure. By purchasing equipment and adding infrastructure. Do not damage, whether intentionally or unintentionally, school facilities and infrastructure. Do not sell school facilities and infrastructure to other parties. Ask the school for permission if you want to borrow school facilities. Return the facilities that have been borrowed properly and on time. Gradually complete and maintain existing infrastructure. The solution to the problem of the MA financing aspect in curriculum management is to budget funds for the next period and make a breakthrough by maximizing existing funds so that the development of students' noble morals

continues to run well. There is no solution that must be provided because there is no problem in the financing aspect.

DISCUSSION

a. Islamic boarding school-based curriculum planning in improving the noble morals of MA Hidayatul Insan students in Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

Planning is a strategic activity to arrange things that need to be done with the resources available. The plan is to determine the company's overall goals and the best way to achieve them. Managers evaluate various alternative plans before taking action, then check whether the chosen plan is appropriate and can be used to achieve company goals. Planning is the most important process of all management functions, because without planning, other functions cannot be carried out. Medium-term curriculum planning or often called micro curriculum is related to a framework regarding learning programs for each semester and class, including determining the number of subjects to be taught. This medium-term curriculum planning is often called a syllabus (its development will be discussed simultaneously with the Learning Implementation Plan or RPP). The syllabus must show details of what students will do during a certain period throughout one semester in each lesson. Short-term curriculum planning is often called a lesson plan and is abbreviated as RPP. RPPs are prepared by teachers individually or in groups relating to the questions of what goals/competencies must be achieved, how to achieve them, and how to find out what they have achieved. Planning in an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum cannot be separated from analysis of the basic references of the Yellow Book as a medium for improving students' noble morals. Regarding improving learning achievement in classical books (yellow), an Islamic boarding school is required to apply integrated curriculum management, because integrated learning has a learning approach that can enable students, both individually and in groups, to actively seek, explore and discover holistic and authentic concepts and principles that where this curriculum model is very suitable for the life of santri/students who are boarded, santri/students are emphasized on living independently and full of responsibility. The integration of the sorogan and troop models by adding innovation to modern learning models will be able to strengthen Islamic boarding school education as an institution that is full of enthusiasm, creative, unique, active, and has its own characteristics

b. Organizing an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum to improve the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

Curriculum organization can be seen from two approaches, namely in a management context and in an academic context. The definition of the word organization itself is a social group that is closed or open from/towards outside parties, which is regulated based on certain rules, which is led/governed by a leader or leader or administrative staff, who can carry out regular and purposeful guidance. . In an organization, it is very necessary to carry out management processes, namely:

- a) Organization of curriculum planning, which is carried out by an institution or curriculum development team;
- b) Organization for implementing the curriculum, both at the regional level and at the madrasa level or educational institution unit that implements the curriculum;
- c) Organization in the curriculum evaluation stage, which involves the parties involved in the curriculum evaluation process.

c. Implementation of an Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

Curriculum implementation is the application or implementation of a curriculum program that has been developed in the previous stage, then tested with implementation and management, while always making adjustments to the field situation and characteristics of students, both intellectual and emotional development. The implementation stage is when the curriculum that has been designed is implemented in practice. Teachers or instructors play a key role in organizing and implementing learning according to the plans that have been prepared. It is important to ensure that the learning strategies, teaching materials and assessments used are in accordance with the goals and vision of the curriculum. The implementation phase also involves continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure that learning is going well.

d. Evaluation of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

Curriculum evaluation is a systematic process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting information/data to determine the extent to which students have achieved learning objectives. Evaluation is carried out after the work process is complete. In this process, assess whether performance is according to plan. At this stage, management evaluates the success and effectiveness of performance, makes clarifications and corrections, and provides alternative solutions to problems that arise in the work process. From the analysis of the description above, it can be concluded that the evaluation of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum has not been optimally used as material for consideration and study in order to make improvements to the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving noble morals.

e. Problems of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

Madrasahs face obstacles in preparing program plans because the existing documents and information are still very limited. One of the main causes is the lack of active role of managers or officers who are specifically responsible for managing educational data and information. Even though there are staff tasked with managing data and information, they are often involved in financial matters involving planning, submissions and financial reporting. As a result, the management of data and information related to educational aspects that are important for

preparing curriculum planning is disrupted and less than optimal

f. Solutions implemented to overcome the problem of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of students at MA Hidayatul Insan, Palangka Raya City and MA Tahfidz Nurul Musthofa Tanjung

To overcome the problems in curriculum management that have been identified, a number of solutions are needed that need to be considered:

- 1) To overcome limitations in terms of documentation, madrasas need to appoint special officers or managers of educational data and information. This manager will be responsible for collecting, storing and maintaining educational documents and information properly. By having a focused data manager, madrasahs can ensure that the information needed for planning educational programs is available in full;
- 2) In an effort to improve teacher professionalism and performance, the government must continue to support teacher professional development programs, welfare guarantees, protection and teacher appreciation. This support can include additional training, access to cutting-edge educational resources, as well as incentives that encourage teachers to improve the quality of learning;
- 3) To overcome the challenges of teachers in the millennial era, there needs to be a comprehensive approach to increasing their competence. Teachers need to be given training that is relevant to current developments, including skills in using educational technology. This support can also include developing curricula that are more suited to the needs of students in the digital era;
- 4) Management of infrastructure needs to be improved by fulfilling relevant standards. Learning facilities, such as laboratories and libraries, must be well managed, equipped with appropriate equipment, and adapted to developments in science and technology;
- 5) In the management of education funds, transparency and accountability must be increased. Guidelines for managing funds, especially School Operational Assistance (BOS) funds, must be adhered to and implemented according to main priorities. The use of BOS funds must be well planned and must not overlap with other funds received by the madrasah. These solutions need to be the focus of attention in curriculum management, which in turn will help improve the quality of education and the performance of educators in madrasas.

CONCLUSION

Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in improving the noble morals of MA students has been implemented based on the national curriculum which is integrated with the values desired by the Islamic boarding school, but has not fully had an impact on improving the noble morals of MA students.

- 1) Islamic boarding school-based curriculum planning has been formulated and determined through stages of deliberation activities involving caregivers, madrasah heads, teacher councils and education staff and is in accordance with planning indicators.

- 2) The organization of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving students' noble morals is carried out by dividing work and workloads which are adjusted to the content of the MA curriculum, and there are the addition of certain subjects that support the improvement of students' noble morals through special subjects, but this is still constrained by educational resources not all of whom are competent in their fields.
- 3) The implementation of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving students' noble morals is carried out based on the national curriculum structure which is integrated with the unique values of Islamic boarding schools with references to classical books, but several problems are still found in this implementation, including the ability of educational resources in explaining material and combining noble moral values originating from classical books, and limited learning resources.
- 4) Evaluation of the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving students' noble morals is still not optimally used as material for consideration and study in making improvements to the Islamic boarding school-based curriculum in improving noble morals.
- 5) The problem of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management in MA is that it is still faced with the constraints of the educational background of teaching staff which is still not in accordance with the lessons being taught, funding which is still insufficient to meet operational learning needs, as well as limited infrastructure and learning resources.
- 6) Solutions to overcome the problems of Islamic boarding school-based curriculum management are carried out by increasing the ability of teaching staff who teach Islamic boarding school specific subjects, collaborating with various parties to explore funding sources, and making efforts to fulfill standardized infrastructure, as well as implementing infrastructure management based on existing regulations.

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